

SCOPING PAPER

CIRCULAR ECONOMY

A NEFI Innovation Hub

NEFI – The Innovation Network for Industrial Transformation

NEFI – New Energy for Industry is an innovation network consisting of over 100 industry partners, 8 research partners, and 4 institutional partners. With 25 research and innovation projects dedicated to industrial transformation in Austria, an investment volume of nearly €100 million has been mobilised.

The goals of NEFI are:

- **Climate Neutrality** – Supplying selected sites with up to 100% renewable energy.
- **Value Creation and Location Security** – Promoting technology development and exports “Made in Austria”.
- **Industrial Resilience** – Ensuring energy supply, optimising processes, and improving infrastructure for Austrian industry.

The solutions developed within NEFI address 53% of the CO₂ emissions expected by 2040 and have the potential to generate an economic benefit of €2.2 billion. Additionally, by 2040, more than 25% of fossil energy imports could be avoided.

Achieving a climate-neutral industry by 2040 requires significant research and development efforts. Essential technologies are not yet fully developed, tested, or scalable to a sufficient extent. To bridge technological gaps and strategically drive innovations along realistic, scenario-based transformation pathways, six Innovation Hubs have been established.

NEFI Innovation Hubs

The NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. Their goal is to initiate high-impact research and innovation projects that support the transition to a climate-neutral industry and position Austria as a technology leader in renewable energy and industrial innovation.

Both large corporations and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as well as research institutions, are invited to participate in the Innovation Hubs.

NEFI Innovation Hubs: value proposition for partners

- ☑ Regular networking and information events: The NEFI Technology Talks present current technologies, trends, and developments.
- ☑ Support throughout the innovation process: From project idea to funding application and impact assessment.
- ☑ Dissemination of results: Effective communication and visibility.
- ☑ Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure.

The NEFI Innovation Hubs focus on the following key areas: CCUS, Circular Economy, CO₂-neutral Gases & Hydrogen, Electrification & Energy Efficiency, Flexibility, and Industrial Symbiosis. These topics have been identified as crucial for achieving industrial climate goals across different industries and scenarios ([NEFI Pathway to Industrial Decarbonisation](#) and [transform.industry - in German](#)).

1. Circular Economy – Current developments and trends

Linear production and consumption patterns lead to a steadily increasing amount of waste, alongside a continuously rising demand for primary raw materials and energy. In a circular economy, material and production cycles are closed through reuse and the use of recycled materials. Options include extending product life cycles on the one hand and, on the other, developing technically and economically viable concepts for recovering and utilising by-product streams and secondary raw materials. The goal must be to maximise resource efficiency while minimising environmental impacts.

Key Trends in Circular Economy are:

- (1) Waste as a resource:** Waste is increasingly being utilised as a valuable resource to reduce Europe's dependence on raw material imports, particularly in relation to providing technologies for the energy transition. Targeted recycling of products such as packaging, electrolyser components, PV panels, and batteries helps to lower import demand. The focus is on advancing collection, sorting, and recycling processes to efficiently recover secondary raw materials from these product groups.
- (2) Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD):** Materials are increasingly being developed according to the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) principle, which prioritises safety, circularity, and sustainability throughout the entire life cycle. The development and use of secondary raw materials can also benefit from this approach, as functionality, safety, as well as economic and environmental sustainability are key decision criteria for their application. Design-to-Recycle is becoming a central concept to facilitate the recovery and reuse of secondary raw materials from products and technology components.
- (3) Regulations in plastic recycling:** Stricter recycling targets for plastic packaging (rising from approximately 31% in 2020 to 55% by 2030) necessitate advancements in collection, sorting, and recycling processes. Furthermore, alternative production pathways for (secondary) plastics are essential to minimise the use of fossil resources, despite the expected massive increase in plastic production—current estimates predict a fourfold rise in plastic manufacturing in the EU by 2050.
- (4) Recycling of energy technology components:** The increasing demand for critical raw materials, metals, and minerals for batteries, PV modules, electrolysers, and electric motors (e.g., permanent magnets) makes efficient recycling processes a key strategy for supply security and sustainability. The development of new technologies for recovering rare metals and the establishment of well-functioning secondary raw material markets are central trends aimed at minimising supply risks—both economically, ecologically, and socially.
- (5) Regulatory framework:** Recycling quotas for plastic packaging and batteries are already established at the EU level. From 2030 onwards, additional requirements for the use of secondary raw materials in batteries and accumulators will come into effect, covering nickel, cobalt, and lithium. However, the current regulatory framework often poses challenges for the use of secondary raw materials, particularly regarding compliance with technical standards and legal requirements (e.g., food contact materials).

2. High-Potential Technologies and Innovations in Circular Economy

In circular economy processes, a wide range of separation, conversion, and processing technologies are used, resulting in significant technological diversity. It is essential that future technology chains meet the following key requirements:

- Direct use of complex feedstocks such as highly viscous suspensions, particulate systems, and multi-component residual material streams
- Selective separation of components from multi-component streams (e.g., sorting, selective extraction of valuable individual components, in-situ product separation from process mixtures, membrane technologies)
- Continuous processes that enable seamless integration with upstream and downstream process steps, ensuring efficient further processing of remaining residues, especially after valuable components have been separated
- Low complexity to facilitate easy integration into existing systems and minimise operational risks
- Smart monitoring and control systems, incorporating AI where necessary and beneficial
- Optimised material and energy transport under sustainable conditions—not necessarily requiring faster processes but technologies that, for example, can shorten the residence times of slow biological processes

Examples of these technological properties can be found across various industries, from plastic, textile, and metal recycling to the recycling of bio-based materials and the valorisation of biogenic residues within the circular economy.

Based on the general trends in the field of circular economy and the above mentioned requirements, the following high-potential technologies and innovations can be identified:

- (1) Intelligent object sorting in plastic recycling:** Precise sorting of complex residual material streams in plastic recycling is essential to ensure that sorted materials are directed into the appropriate recovery pathways. Here, an AI-assisted control system can be very useful, enabling accurate identification and separation. Additionally, seamless integration with downstream process flows is necessary to efficiently handle the resulting material volumes.
- (2) Processing complex viscous suspensions using new reactor technologies:** in the processing of complex residual materials, such as food, biogenic residues, textiles, or wastewater, the complexity of the media presents a significant challenge. Time-consuming separation, material drying, and subsequent dilution increase energy and resource consumption. In the future, technologies will be needed that can directly and continuously process slurry residual material streams, while efficiently separating valuable substances, such as in hydrolysis or separation processes. These innovations will make waste recovery significantly more resource-efficient and energy-efficient.
- (3) Energy-efficient recovery of valuable materials using membrane technologies and selective separation:** The energy-efficient recovery of valuable materials from waste and wastewater, particularly from mixed waste streams such as batteries, scrap, and wastewater, is a central challenge. Selective separation of critical raw materials requires cost-effective and efficient processes. In this context, membrane technologies and electrochemical processes will play a key role.

3. Main Research Questions in the field of Circular Economy

As part of the NEFI Innovation Hub for Circular Economy, projects will be developed to address the following research questions:

- How can circular economy processes be operated in an energy- and resource-efficient manner? Circular economy processes involve much more complex feedstocks than traditional processes based on hydrocarbons or other raw materials available in high purity. Selective separation of valuable materials is essential to obtain pure materials from complex media in as few process steps as possible. The more selectively valuable materials can be separated from mixtures in a single process step, the lower the chemical and energy demand for the overall process, and the more economically future processes can operate.
- How can efficient and resilient value creation networks be designed to enable optimal (cascade) utilisation of valuable materials? How can parallel value creation pathways be developed and implemented by leveraging the synergies that emerge?
- For which substrates is a meaningful circular economy possible, and how can the implementation of processing steps in the overall context lead to climate-positive effects and an improvement of the overall environmental balance?
- How can chemicals and operational materials in circular economy processes be optimised according to the principles of Green Chemistry to make the entire life cycle of circulated products sustainable and environmentally friendly?
- How can intelligent logistics systems optimise the collaboration of local actors to make regional value chains and networks in the circular economy efficient and sustainable?
- How many product cycles are maximally possible in the circular economy for various products, and what are the impacts of repeated recycling processes on material properties, quality, and sustainability?
- How can ecological, economic, and social aspects be integrated into the evaluation of innovative circular economy processes to ensure holistic sustainability performance (SSbD)?

4. Out-of-Scope Topics and Collaborative Overlaps

The following topics and industries are outside the focus area of the Innovation Hub:

- **Defined CCU Pathways:** CCU technologies that focus solely on CO₂ capture and the synthesis of CO₂ (e.g., in combination with H₂ to produce short-lived chemical products) are not part of the NEFI Innovation Hub Circular Economy but are addressed within the NEFI Innovation Hub CCUS.

Through cooperation and alignment between the NEFI Innovation Hubs, synergies can be leveraged, technological trends identified, and innovations accelerated.

The NEFI Innovation Hub for Circular Economy expects overlaps with the following NEFI Innovation Hubs:

- **CCUS and CO₂-neutral Gases & Hydrogen:** At the end of a cascade of raw material use (downcycling), thermal recovery often takes place, releasing CO₂. To achieve CO₂ neutrality, this CO₂ must be captured and, if necessary, synthesised into chemical products with H₂. This leads to complex production cycles that overlap with the CCUS and CO₂ Neutral Gases & Hydrogen Hubs. There are also overlaps in the use of CO₂ from the air as a raw material for circular economy processes, such as the carboxylation of organic substrates.
- **Industrial Symbiosis:** The goal of industrial symbiosis is, among other things, the cooperation between two (or more) companies to exchange energy, materials, and/or by-products. A waste stream from one company can become a material input stream for another. Therefore, a circular economy is not possible without leveraging the advantages of industrial symbiosis, and there is an overlap between the Industrial Symbiosis and Circular Economy Hubs.
- **Electrification and Energy Efficiency:** Overlaps occur mainly in the areas of energy supply and energy management of the circular economy processes to be developed, with a focus on maximising energy efficiency. In addition, electricity is the main energy source for numerous recycling processes (e.g., sorting, electrochemical processes). It is important to assess how this plays a role in the electrification of industry or what systemic role circular economy processes can take on.

5. Hub Co-Leads & Contact Persons

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